

STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE TEXTS OF WORKS OF ART (ENGLISH AND UZBEK AUTHORS)

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ABSTRACT

This article presents basic attitudes and theories of phraseological units in the English language, attempts to provide a better understanding of the phraseology, and explores structural and semantic peculiarities of phraseological units in English contexts. The aim of this volume, then, is to explore the cultural dimension of a wide range of preconstructed or semi-preconstructed word combinations in English. These include highly opaque multiword units of the kick-the bucket type, collocations, irreversible binominals, phrasal verbs, compounds, metaphorical expressions, similes, proverbs, familiar quotations, catchphrases, clichés, slogans, expletives, and discourse markers such as politeness formulae – all of which have been subsumed under phraseology, or under idiom in the Anglo-American linguistic tradition. In this article the basic types of phraseological units are analyzed relating to the degree of idiomaticity in the process of learning a foreign language. The authors have tried to define the types of phraseological units by using numerous examples.

The word “phraseology” for instance, has very different meaning in this country and in Great Britain or The United States. In our linguistic literature the term has come to be used for the while ensemble of expressions where the meaning of one element is dependent on the other, irrespective of the structure and properties of the unit; with other authors it denotes only such set expressions which, as distinguished from idioms, do not possess expressiveness or emotional colouring and also vice versa; only those that are imaginative expressive and emotional; N.N Amasova overcomes the subjectiveness of the two last mentioned approaches when she insists on term being applicable only to what she calls fixed context units, units in which it is impossible to substitute any of the components without changing the meaning only of the whole unit, but also of the elements that remain intact.¹ O.S. Ahmanova has repeatedly

¹ Амосова Н.Н. Основы английской фразеологии Л. 1963. Стр. 68.

insisted on the semantic integrity of such phrases prevailing over the structural separateness of their elements² A.V. Kunin³ lays stress on the structural separateness of the elements in a phraseological unit, on the change of meaning in the whole as compared with its elements taken separately and on a certain minimum stability. All these authors use the same word “phraseology” to denote the branch of linguistics studying the word-groups they have in mind. In modern English Phraseology is one of disputable items, and it seems that this linguistic discipline is not going to lose its actuality. The results of researches that have been done on phraseology show that this problem has not been solved yet. Consequently, there are several terms that are used in phraseology. Let’s study them individually: idioms, set expressions, set phrases, proverbs.

The actuality of this research paper is explained by the deep interest in learning phraseological units in the context. Language is a complex object and it may be defined not only as a means of communication but also as a product and basic sphere of human cognitive activity. Phraseology is one of the most relevant and frequent topics of modern anthropocentric research. The most important impulse in the formation of phraseological units is the linguistic environment of human life activity. For the first time, phraseology was used in the study of literature. While translating some fiction from one language into another it became impossible to translate inseparable word combinations. Then the phraseological unities in those languages were researched. The term phraseology was first used in philology in 1558 by the English literary scholar Neander. While translating the literary works Neander had to use this term. Although the biggest part of phraseological materials are included in vocabulary and other sources, the research works on the theory of phraseology have been rarely met in the sources concerning linguistics (L. Smith, D. Curry, W. Ball, Ch.Bally). Up to now the matters of English phraseology have been studied within grammar, stylistics, lexicography and the history of language. Later phraseology has been studied as a branch of lexicology. As the linguistics developed, nowadays phraseology has been admitted and is being researched as an independent branch of linguistics in most languages. It is worth pointing out that a number of Eastern European and Russian scholars researched this field in their works. The vocabulary of a language is enriched no longer handiest through words but additionally through word mixtures which might be differently known as. Some of them consult with unfastened word combinations, the others are referred to as set expressions and the term phraseological gadgets are often used for them. Phraseological gadgets, including proverbs, sayings, clichés, quotations in addition to various varieties of allusions may be used for stylistic reason.

Phraseology has attracted rapidly increasing interest from a wide range of language related disciplines, which has yet to coalesce into an agreed set of terms and frameworks. This method is appeared as necessary in studies specializing in stylistic capabilities of phrasing, which unavoidably require close evaluation of the manufacturing of man or woman audio system and writers as opposed to the processing of big corpora en masse. A phraseological

² Ахманова Н.Н. Фразеология английского языка Л. 1972 стр. 56.

³ Кунин.А.В. Фразеология современного английского языка. М, 1972 стр. 88.

unit is a strong, cohesive combination of phrases with a totally or partially figurative that means.

Phraseological units are word-groups that cannot be made in the process of speech, they exist in the language as ready-made units. They are compiled in special dictionaries. The same as words phraseological units express a single notion and are used in a sentence as one part of it. American and British lexicographers call such units "idioms". Phraseological units can be classified according to the ways they are formed, according to the degree of the motivation of their meaning, according to their structure and according to their part-of-speech meaning.

Their constant characteristic features are:

Linguistic stability ·

Semantic unity ·

Intact syntactical structure

In different words, phraseological unit is a fixed phrase-mixture wherein that means of the complete doesn't rely upon the which means of its additives. Syntactically the members of the family in a phraseological unit are those of a free word mixture. +

Ex.: to be born with a silver spoon inside the mouth; to drag any individual's leg, to kick the bucket.

Phraseological devices are crystallized metaphors the expressiveness of that's regularly intensified through parallelism, antithesis, and alliteration.

Phraseologists not ought to guard themselves from accusations that they may be wasting their time on trivial phenomena: phraseological units of a wide variety permeate regular language use at some point of all linguistic registers: in regular speech, journalism, educational prose, literature, political or diplomatic speech and writing etc. Phrasing plays crucial mental and cultural roles in language processing and social cohesiveness. The usage of phraseology can be visible to make a contribution to readability of expression and ease of comprehension in formal registers, and simplicity of linguistic composition in spontaneous speech. Using phraseology contributes to a socially convergent fashion of speech or writing. Pawley (1985) points out that «likely the big majority of normal institutions are denoted by means of phraseological expressions» in the front door/back door, visit church, leave faculty and many others. In emotive prose phraseological gadgets are used in author's speech, in character's speech and in internal monologue. Phraseological units, which can be used in character's speech help to learn about the character, his manners of speech and approximately his emotional country. The phraseological units which can be utilized in internal monologue assist apprehend his interior qualities.

Phraseological units are habitually defined as non-motivated word-groups that cannot be freely made up in speech but are reproduced as a ready-made system. This definition proceeds from the assumption that the essential features of phraseological units are considered to be the stability of the lexical components. [3, p. 942] It is frequently assumed that unlike components of free word-groups which may vary due to the needs of communication, words of phraseological units are reproduced as single unchangeable collocations. Taking into account mainly the degree of idiomaticity phraseological units may be classified into three big groups: phraseological fusions, phraseological unities and phraseological collocations. The meaning of the components has no connections whatsoever,

at least synchronically, with the meaning of the whole group. Idiomaticity is, as a rule, combined with complete stability of the lexical components and the grammatical structure of the fusion. Phraseological units, which arose as a result of a complete rethinking of the variable combinations, can serve: “big wig” – means an important person (lit. a large 31 artificial hair); “that cock will not fight” – means this number will not work (lit. this cock will not be able to fight) or breakers ahead! - Danger! Beware! [38, 249].

Many phraseological units are created due to a rethinking of stable combinations of a non phraseological character. It can include, for instance, professionalism and terms used in a literal sense. For example: “hold in leash” – (keep in check, in obedience), (lit. keep the letters on the pack (greyhounds)); or “Go off at half-cock” – means “To act or speak hurriedly, thoughtlessly” [17, 49]. Phraseological collocations are motivated but they are made up of words possessing specific lexical valency which accounts for a certain degree of stability in such word-groups. In phraseological collocations variability of member words is strictly limited. There are plenty of phraseological hyperboles and exaggerations: “Make a mountain out of a molehill” - make an elephant from a fly [17, 68].

Except this there are phraseological units with different stylistic colors. They add a new color to the speech, or mainly, may be used in the literature in order to catch listener’s attention, or to create an interesting situation: A) ironic turns: “have a soul above buttons” - consider the work performed below than its real value; 32

underestimate; a fat lot of – “very little” [17, 39]; B) jocular turns: the clerk of the weather (changeable person, who changes very often as weather”, “In one’s birthday suit”- “naked “ Has the cat got your tongue? “Have you swallowed your tongue?” [38, 244]; C) vulgar expressions: Damn your eyes! Means “Damn you!” [17, 89]. Phraseological units take an important place in Uzbek language. There are two types of word combinations in Uzbek language: Free word combinations and Constant word combinations. Constant word combinations are sometimes called Phraseological unities are such combinations that are in ready form in the language, and separately do not have any meaning but, whole combination has a specific meaning. The translation of phraseological units is not an easy matter as it depends on several factors: different combinability of words, homonymy, synonymy, polysemy of phraseological units and presence of falsely identical units which make it necessary to take into account the context. Besides, a large number of phraseological units have stylistic – expressive components in meaning, which usually have a specific national feature. So, it’s just necessary to get acquainted with the main principles of the general theory of phraseology.

The following types of phraseological units may be observed: presumes and idioms. A unit of constant context consisting of a dependant and a constant indicators may be called a phrase me.

An Idiom is a unit of constant context which is characterized by an integral meaning of the whole and by weakened meanings of the components, and in which is dependent and the indication elements are identical and equal to the whole lexical structural of the phrase.

And type of a phraseological unit can be presented a definite micro – system. In the process of translating phraseological units functional adequate linguistic units are selected by comparing two specific linguistic principles. These principles reveal elements of likeness and

distinction. Certain part of these systems may correspond in form and context or have no adequacy.

The main types of phraseological conformities are as follows:

1. Complete conformities.
2. Partial conformities.
3. Absence of conformities.

I. Complete coincidence of form and context in phrasiological units is rarely met with.

1. Black frost (phrase me) – qorasovuq.
2. To bring oil to fire (idiom) – alangagayog' quymoq.

II. Partial conformities of phraseological units in two language assume lexical, grammatical and lexica – grammatical differences with identity of meaning, but differ in lexical composition, morphologic number and syntactic arrangement of word order. One may find:

A. Partial lexical conformities by lexic parameters;

No worth a bean – bir gurunch donasicha, sariq chaqaga ham arzimaslik. There the word “bean” means “loviya” in Uzbek, but we have changed “bean” loviya to “gurunch”. In this translation we take into account the social life, national meal of Uzbek country, as “rise” – “gurunch” is more widely used in Uzbekistan. To get out of bed o the wrong feet. (Idiom). Chap yoni bilanturmoq.

B. Partial conformities by the grammatical parametries:

a. Differing as to morphological arrangement. (number)

To fish in troubled waters.(idiom) Loyqa suvda baliq tutmoq. To agree like cats and dogs. (idiom) It – mushukdek yashamoq.

b. Differing as to syntactical arrangement.

Strike while iron is hot.

Temirniqizig'idabos.

All in not gold that glitters.

Barcha yaltiragan narsalar oltin emas.

C. Absence conformities:

Many English phraseological units have no phraseological conformities in Uzbek and Russian. In the first instance this concerns phraseological units based on really. When translating units of this find it's advisable to use the following types of translation. A. A verbatim word for word translation.

B. Translation by analogy.

C. Descriptive translation. Verbatim translation is possible when the way of thinking doesn't bear a specific national feature:

Eg.To call thing by their true names. Har narsani o'z nomi bilan atamoq. The arms race (phraseme) Qurollanishpoygasi.

Cold war – (idiom). Sovuqurush.

Translation by analogy.

This way of translation is resorted to when the phraseological units has a specific national realize.

1) "Dick" said the dwarf, thrashing his head in at the door, - "my pet", "my pencil", apple of my eye, hey! - Dik, azizam, tolibim, ko'zginamning nuri, hursandligidan xitob qildim ikki odam eshikdan boshini suqib. 2) To pool somebody's leg (idiom) Mazah qilmoq, oyog'idanchalmoq.

Descriptive translation.

Descriptive translation that is translating phraseological units by a free combination of words, it is possible when the phraseological units has a particular national feature and has no analogue in the language, it is to be translated into;

1. To enter the House: (Phraseme) Parlamenta'zosibo'lmoq.

2. To cross the floor of the House: (idiom). Bir partiyadan boshqa partiyaga o'tib ketmoq.

In the examples given about the word "House" is translated as "Parlament" and "Partiya" as a political word. Phraseological units cannot be freely made up in speech but are reproduced as readymade units.

The lexical components in phraseological units are stable and they are non – motivated; that is its meaning cannot be decoded from the meaning of its components and they don't allow their lexical components to be changed or substituted⁴.

In phraseological units the individual components don't seem to possess any lexical meaning outside the word group.

Eg.Red tape, to get rid of, to take place.

To lead the dance to take care.

Conclusion

Functionally and semantically inseparable units are usually called phraseological units. Phraseological units can not be freely made up in speech but are reproduced as readymade units.

The lexical components in phraseological units are stable and they are non – motivated i.e. its meaning cannot be deduced from the meaning of its components and they do not allow their lexical components be charged or substituted.

In phraseological units the individual components do not seem to possess any lexical meaning outside the word group.

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